

**A review of the status of *Poanes massasoit hughii* Clark, 1931,
confirming status as a range-wide variant form of
P. massasoit (Scudder, 1863).**

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ABSTRACT: *Poanes massasoit hughii* was described as a new subspecies (Clark, 1931) based on a common, predominant phenotype occurring in Maryland, differentiated from specimens of the nominotypical phenotype occurring in eastern Massachusetts. Clark apparently had very limited access to specimens, thus unable to see that the “*hughii*” phenotype occurs throughout the range of *P. massasoit*. Subsequent treatment of *hughii* as either a subspecies or form of *P. massasoit* varies across the literature. This paper utilizes cartographic analysis, coupled with internet-based imagery, to determine the distribution of the *hughii* phenotype within the range of *P. massasoit*.

INTRODUCTION

Samuel Scudder (1863) initially described new species *Hesperia massasoit* from a small series of specimens from Massachusetts and Connecticut (**Fig. 1**). The distinguishing feature was described for the secondaries beneath: “The central portion of the wing is entirely taken up by a large sulphur-yellow spot of irregular shape”.

65. *HESPERIA MASSASOIT* nov. sp. ♂ Above very dark-brown with a mulberry lustre, having no markings except occasionally a faint small yellowish spot or two on middle of secondaries, fringe slightly paler, yellowish around the inner angle of secondaries.

Beneath: *Primaries* hardly so dark as above, with reddish-yellow scales scattered along the costal border, and on the outer border, especially toward the apex; two very small spots of same color, about midway between extremity of cell and apex of wing, with two large ones at the middle of the wing, the inner a little lower than the outer: *Secondaries* dark-brown with profusely scattered reddish-yellow scales, especially toward the inner angle; the central portion of the wing is entirely taken up by a large sulphur-yellow spot of irregular shape, formed of a straight broad band, extending between the subcostal and median nervures, nearly to the hind border, cut across by an incurved line of reddish-yellow scales just below the divarication of the subcostal, and crossed by a transverse broad band, just beyond the middle of the wing, extending from costal to submedian nervures, cut across by the reddish-yellow scales following the nervures, and bent somewhat upon either side of the first band.

♀ Differs from ♂ only in having the markings of the under surface of the primaries repeated above, and a faint transverse band of distant reddish-yellow spots across the middle of secondaries. Expanse of wings 1.1—1.4 in. Very rare; I have seen it only from Carver, Mass., Mr. Shurtleff, Conn., Mr. Edwards, and New-England, Museum of Comp. Zoology.

Fig. 1. Original description as *Hesperia massasoit* from Scudder (1863).

Scudder (1863) did not illustrate the holotype of *Hesperia massasoit* in the original description, nor did he provide life history information. The presumed male holotype is now available online via the Museum of Comparative Zoology (**Fig. 2**). A female was later illustrated in Scudder (1889) (**Fig. 3**). The original description indicated the TL in Carver, MA. (Plymouth County).

Fig. 2. Presumed holotype of *Hesperia massasoit* (Scudder, 1863), courtesy Museum of Comparative Zoology. Accessible at: [IMG_172114.JPG \(3456×5184\) \(harvard.edu\)](#) and [IMG_172115.JPG \(3456×5184\) \(harvard.edu\)](#)

Fig. 3. *Poanes massasoit* ♀ from Scudder (1889).

The characteristic feature of *massasoit* is the broad yellow patch on the ventral side of the hindwings. Scudder’s 1889 figure shows a broader patch on the illustrated female, than on the “type” housed in the collection of the Museum of Comparative Zoology. Specimens of *massasoit* that were examined indicate no appreciable difference in ventral markings between males and females. However, the females tend to have more well-developed yellow marks on the dorsum, than do the males which are mostly dark. The present analysis is focused on the ventral patch.

In Scudder (1889), the author provided limited life history information, describing *massasoit* as a characteristic member of the Alleghenian fauna, and states that the western limits of its range are uncertain, but listing such states as Texas and Colorado. These western localities require verification, as no modern records or specimens exist nor were specimens available from these states via online imagery or literature. Scudder stated that the species is double brooded, based on early appearance in the first half of June, with a second brood appearing in the second week of July, flying until after the middle of August. This is certainly in error, as all recent observations indicate it is univoltine, flying from June through August. The habitat is described as “swampy places”, including cranberry bogs. Scudder admits, “We are wholly ignorant of its early stages”, thus the need for additional information. More recent observations limit its presence to association with the host *Carex stricta* (Tussock Sedge), generally in open or shrubby wetlands, or within small stands of the host in forested habitat.

Poanes massasoit hughii (Clark, 1931) was subsequently described as a new subspecies from the southern part of the species range (Figs. 4, 5):

1. *Poanes massasoit hughii*, subsp. nov.

Resembling *P. m. massasoit*, but slightly larger and darker, the female with the yellow markings above reduced to small spots and partly, or sometimes completely, absent. Beneath with the costal and outer border of the fore wings and the ground color of the hind wings much darker and more reddish than in *P. m. massasoit*, and the yellow markings on the hind wings less extensive. Yellow markings on the hind wings beneath consisting of a broad yellow band, often more or less obscured, except for the inner end and the outer third or fourth, with rusty, as wide as the interspace which basally extends for a short distance within the cell and outwardly ends at a distance from the outer border which is somewhat greater than the length of the fringe; above the outer third of this band is a small yellow oblong spot not twice as broad as long with sometimes a similar or smaller one above it; between the outer end of the band and the abdominal border of the wing is a series of two or three oblong spots which are usually about twice as long as broad.

Locality.—Beltsville, Maryland; bog between the railway station and the experiment farm of the Bureau of Animal Industry, U. S. Department of Agriculture; Hugh Upham Clark, collector, July 15, 1928.

Fig. 4. Original description of *Poanes massasoit hughii* Clark (1931).

FIG. 1. 1, *P. massasoit massasoit* Scudder, ♂, underside, Weston, Mass., July 9, 1923; 2, Do.; 3, Do., ♀; 4, *P. massasoit*, var. *hughii* Clark, ♂, upperside, Beltsville, Md., July 15, 1928, type; 5, Do., ♂, underside, type; 6, Do., ♂, paratype, underside; 7, Do., ♂, paratype; 8, Do., ♀, underside; allotype; 9, Do., ♀, paratype.

Fig. 5. Original illustrations courtesy of Annals of the Carnegie Museum.

Clark (1931, 1932), in his description of *hughi*, compared his type series of specimens from Beltsville (Prince Georges County), MD. against a small series of nominotypical *massasoit* from a bog in Weston (Middlesex County), MA. (**Fig 5**), stating that the specimens from Beltsville averaged slightly larger, with the ground color being uniformly darker (blackish brown) in both sexes and the males showing violet reflections. Clark apparently had access to a very limited number of specimens from Massachusetts to compare to new subspecies *hughi*. The illustrated specimens from Weston displayed rather strikingly well-developed ventral patches (**Fig. 5**), much more so than the original holotype of *massasoit* (**Fig. 2**). Upon closer examination, the holotype of *massasoit* (**Fig. 2**) shows a slight tendency toward intermediate characters in development of the ventral patch. Clark did note that adults of *hughi* in central Maryland have greatly reduced yellow spots on the ventral and dorsal sides of the forewings, whereas in nominotypical *massasoit*, the forewings of females show a series of well-developed spots both dorsally and ventrally. However, these features vary widely across the species range. Also, Clark's description of Beltsville specimens being darker with violet reflections appears to reflect the fresh condition of specimens near where Clark resided, as opposed to what are presumed to be older specimens from Massachusetts.

My initial goal was to evaluate whether *hughi* does, in fact, represent a subspecific taxon, limited to the area in central Maryland immediately north of Washington D.C., or if *hughi* simply represented a variable form within the greater range of *P. massasoit*. Over a period of several years, I have tried to find a suitable "bog" habitat in the area immediately adjacent to the present-day Beltsville (MARC) rail station and the Greenbelt Rail Yard in Prince George's County. The late Richard "Dick" Smith (pers. corr.) similarly tried to relocate the original bog described by Clark, but was unable to find it. There are several small wetland habitats in the immediate area associated with the Indian Creek drainage in Beltsville, MD., but none with suitable growth of the known host *Carex stricta*. Any formerly desirable wet habitats are now long gone, either having been developed, paved over, or left in somewhat of a "natural" state but overgrown with trees or invasive grasses and brambles such as *Rubus fruticosus* (Blackberry) or *Rosa multiflora* (Multiflora Rose). There are considerable areas to the north and east of Beltsville where wetland habitats are evident in satellite imagery. However, from personal experience, many of those wetlands are inaccessible, or on posted properties. Thus, it was not possible to ascertain if the characters of *hughi*, in a larger series from the TL would hold up to the original description.

Clark (1932) gives description of the habitat of *hughi*, stated to be "boggy meadows with sphagnum adjacent to woods". The butterfly is described as being locally abundant. The immature stages are reportedly able to withstand frequent flooding of the habitat following heavy rainfalls. The flight period is throughout the month of July. I have found them in two locations in central Maryland in fen habitats dominated by the host *Carex stricta*. One of these locations, at Harmans, MD (Howard County) was eventually overgrown with a tall sedge or grass, no doubt invasive, that crowded out the host sedges, which had entirely disappeared. These habitats are very sensitive to changes in ground water table, changes in the landscape, and urban precipitation drainage remediation; also, to urbanization in general. However, the Harmans colony, and a colony at Daisy, MD (Howard County), well-known to local lepidopterologists, produced an adequate series of specimens, as well as additional observations of the ventral phenotype.

My field observations in the two locations over several years indicated that the *hughi* variant was indeed the predominant phenotype in the study region immediately north of Washington D.C., though intermediates to the nominotypical form are frequent. No nominotypical variants were ever found. One would be tempted to assume this would support status of subspecific rank, albeit in a tiny range.

While Scudder originally described the western range of *P. massasoit* as far west as Colorado (no doubt in error), Nebraska and Texas (no doubt in error), interestingly Clarke included in his original 1931 description, a note by W. J. Holland, indicating that several specimens of form *hughi* from Nebraska were located in the collection of W. H. Edwards, and three specimens from South Dakota were identified in the

Ehrmann Collection of the Carnegie Museum of Natural History. Vanessa Verdecia at the Carnegie Museum indicated there are five specimens labelled “Nebr.” in the W. H. Edwards collection, indicated as subspecies *hughi*, but without data. These specimens likely predate Scudder (1863) and may be the source of the Nebraska reference. Neither Johnson (1973), Neck (1996), or Fisher (2017) list *massasoit* in their publications for Colorado, Nebraska and Texas. However, recent evidence of *P. massasoit* in Nebraska was posted to the Nebraska Lepidoptera website (<https://nebraskalepidoptera.com/massasoit2/>), showing the *hughi* variant in the eastern part of the state.

Unfortunately, both Scudder and Clark had limited access to specimens in their days. With the advent of the internet, imagery has become widely available and reliance on often difficult-to-access institutional collections is no longer a hindrance to avocational studies as in pre-internet days.

Scudder’s description of *massasoit* from southeastern Massachusetts is based on the very broad yellow patch on the ventral hindwing. This phenotype is present throughout New England, but is also present range-wide, except in central Maryland where the *hughi* phenotype is predominant. However, in examining imagery posted to [iNaturalist.org](https://www.inaturalist.org) (iNat) and [Butterfliesandmoths.org](https://www.butterfliesandmoths.org) (BAMONA), a different distributional picture emerges, one which often reflects, to some extent, photographic bias of imaging a single specimen at a site, thus leading to an incomplete picture of regional variation. Examination of specimens in the Smithsonian’s National Museum of Natural History (NMNH) likely also reflects incomplete sampling. However, examination of imagery on the web, in literature, and in collections, pointed to the need for an adequate distributional study to determine if the *hughi* phenotype represents a subspecific taxon.

SUBSEQUENT LITERATURE TREATMENT OF *HUGHI*

McDunnough (1938) listed *hughi* at subspecies rank. Macy & Shepard (1941) list “race *hughi*” and indicate a range of New Jersey, Maryland, Georgia, Nebraska and South Dakota. The Georgia report is certainly in error, as Harris (1972) does not list *P. massasoit* for that state. H. Clark & L. F. Clark (1951) included subspecies *hughi* for Virginia, and though there were no records at the time, suggested that it will “probably” be found in Virginia. Klots (1951) listed subspecies *hughi* but commented: “If this is a valid subspecies it cannot come from so wide an area as New Jersey, Maryland, Georgia, Nebraska, and South Dakota as cited; if it does, it is merely a color variety.” Tietz (1952) listed *hughi* for Pennsylvania at subspecies rank. Forbes (1960) listed “var. *hughi*” from Beltsville, MD, but lists the range of *P. massasoit* extending west to Wisconsin, Colorado and Texas (certainly in error for CO and TX). In the first Synonymic List of the Lepidopterists’ Society, dos Passos (1964) listed *hughi* at subspecies rank. Tietz (1972) listed *hughi* at subspecies rank. In Simmons & Anderson (1980), the authors suggested a cline between nominotypical *massasoit* and ssp. *hughi* along the Fall Line separating the Coastal Plain from the Piedmont in Maryland. Miller & Brown (1981) listed “*hughi*” as a form; a status maintained in the Ferris (1989) Supplement. In Hodges (1983), *hughi* is listed in the synonymy under *Poanes massasoit*. Pelham (2008) [including annual updates through 2023] lists *hughi* as a subjective synonym under *Poanes massasoit*. Pohl & Nanz (2023) list *hughi* as a subjective synonym under *Poanes m. massasoit*.

Of special interest is a paper by Anderson & Simmons (1976) in the Journal of the Lepidopterists’ Society. The authors described new subspecies *Poanes massasoit chermocki* from Dorchester County, MD. in which they treated *hughi* as a subspecies. They made comparisons between new subspecies *chermocki* and *hughi*, and suggested that there is a north-south cline in which *hughi* represents an intergrade between nominotypical *massasoit* of the north, and *chermocki* of the south. The authors only compared specimens of *hughi* from northern Maryland to new subspecies *chermocki* from the Delmarva Peninsula, providing the justification that “Clark (1932) has already very adequately compared *P. m. massasoit* and *P. m. hughi*. By

thus limiting their comparison to northern and southern Maryland, and relying on Clark, the authors failed to note the presence of the *hughi* variant northward in Massachusetts and elsewhere.

Though beyond the scope of this paper, is an interesting paper by Shapiro (1971), discussing the postglacial biogeography of several marsh dwelling butterflies and what he referred to as the “Great Lakes-Northern Coastal Plain disjunction” occurring in many butterfly species. This post-Wisconsin glaciation disjunction appears as an odd distribution on either side of the Appalachian Mountains which appears to be a dividing region in which there are no records of the studied butterflies. In focusing discussion on the distribution of *Poanes viator*, Shapiro notes that the range of *viator* is neatly divided into a Coastal Plain element (subspecies *zizaniae*) and a Great Lakes element (nominated *viator*) approximately along the south edge of the Wisconsin glaciation, a pattern followed by the other Hesperid butterflies in the study. All of the Hesperid butterflies in Shapiro’s study are limited to marsh habitats, and utilize either sedges (Cyperaceae) or grasses (Gramineae), and are univoltine in midsummer. Shapiro believed that populations of the studied species travelled westward through a corridor of the Mohawk and Hudson Valleys of central New York to repopulate the Great Lakes region after the retreat of the Wisconsin glaciation. *Poanes massasoit* also shows this disjunct distribution, as evidenced on the distributional maps in Figs. 7, 8 and 9 of the present study, and Shapiro notes that populations on either side of the disjunction are virtually identical except for a single relict population in central New York state, which are uniquely different by having a more heavily-patterned dorsum.

METHODOLOGY

Specimens were examined from a variety of web-based imagery, primarily iNat and BAMONA. Additional imagery was found on a broad range of individual online photographic galleries, too numerous to mention. Specimens from the NMNH collection were examined, as well as from the American Museum of Natural History and a small series in my personal collection. The three basic variants are illustrated in Fig. 6, representing nominotypical *massasoit* (A), *hughi* (C) and intermediates (B).

Fig. 6. Three basic variant forms of *P. massasoit*: (A) nominotypical form; (B) intermediate form; (C) form *hughi*. All figures represent the ventral hindwing.

The distribution of these variants was then mapped by county or regional municipality (Canada) in order to better determine the range of each (Figs. 7, 8, 9). The resulting distributional maps are rather revealing, showing the three phenotypes (Fig. 6) to be widespread variant forms throughout the range of *massasoit*.

Fig. 7. Distribution of *hughii* phenotype (ORANGE). Complete range of *P. massasoit* is shown as GRAY counties. Inset shows range in Ontario, Canada.

Fig. 8. Distribution of intermediate variants (ORANGE). Complete range of *P. massasoit* is shown as GRAY counties. Inset shows range in Ontario, Canada.

Fig. 9. Distribution of nominotypical *massasoit* phenotype (ORANGE). Complete range of *P. massasoit* is shown as GRAY counties. Inset shows range in Ontario, Canada.

CONCLUSION

The distributional maps indicate that across the range of *P. massasoit* a broad range of variation occurs including the nominotypical form, the *hughi* phenotype and intermediate variants. Even at the TL of *massasoit* in southeastern Massachusetts, a broad range of variation exists, with the nominotypical phenotype at one end of the spectrum and the *hughi* phenotype at the other end. The conclusion derived here confirms that *hughi* essentially is a common variant form of *P. massasoit* that occurs range-wide.

The extent of the yellow ventral patch in *P. massasoit* displays a broad range of variation (**Fig. 10**). While the nominotypical phenotype, *hughi* phenotype and intermediates occur across the species range, variants displaying minimal development of the yellow patch occur at the extreme southeastern end of the species range. Subspecies *chermocki* Anderson & Simmons, 1976 (**Fig. 10 E**) is primarily limited to a very small area on the Delmarva Peninsula of Maryland. The ventral patch is reduced to a row of postmedian spots and a weakly developed discal spot. Thus, *hughi* can be considered to be an intermediate form to *chermocki* (**Fig. 10**). Considerably darker is the variant form “*suffusa*” (**Fig. 10 F**), known mainly from along the Atlantic Coastal Plain from New Jersey to Maryland. Darker yet are rare melanic forms showing no trace of the ventral patch (**Fig. 10 G**).

Fig. 10. Variation in *P. massasoit*: (A) Nominotypical subspecies *massasoit*, Montgomery Co., MD. (B) Intermediate variant, Providence Co., R.I. (C) Variant form *hughi*, Providence Co., R.I. (D) Intermediate variant, Howard Co., MD. (E) Subspecies *chermocki*, Dorchester Co., MD. (F) Form “*suffusa*”, Dorchester Co., MD. (G) Melanic variant, Dorchester Co., MD. All views ventral side.

While not justifiable as a subspecies, the *hughi* phenotype is the primary form in central Maryland. With the complete absence of the nominotypical form within the documented *hughi* colonies in Maryland, some local lepidopterologists still treat *hughi* as a localized subspecies, even though it is a widespread form throughout the entire species range.

A WORD ON *POANES MASSASOIT CHERMOCKI* ANDERSON & SIMMONS, 1976

While in the process of researching the distribution of *P. massasoit*, it was learned that the isolate subspecies *chermocki* has not been found in the type locality in Dorchester County, Maryland, or one additional location in Delaware for several decades as of this writing. Last reports from the TL were from about 2007 despite intensive, repeated searches. Reports from several naturalists stated that the accessible roadside habitat at the TL has been cut and herbicide possibly applied. The portion of the habitat possibly still supporting the TL colony is essentially inaccessible. However, records of the *chermocki* phenotype have historically been found as singletons in other portions of the species range, no doubt showing that *chermocki* is yet a more extreme variant in those areas. Records of *chermocki* are from: Delaware: Sussex Co. (NatureServe Explorer, accessed April 1, 2024). Maryland: Cecil Co. (“We note that in our collections of *hughi* from north central Maryland forms similar to *chermocki* occur at a rate of approximately 4 per cent.” (Anderson & Simmons, 1976); Dorchester Co. (TL); Howard Co. (one specimen within a *hughi*-dominant colony, collected by H. Pavulaan); Prince Georges County (one specimen near the *hughi* TL (Clark & Clark, 1932). Michigan: Wayne Co. (collected by M. C. Nielsen (Lepid. Soc. Season Summary, accessed April 1, 2024)). Nebraska: Boone Co. (S. Spomer collection).

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ADDITIONAL SOURCES OF IMAGERY

Butterflies and Moths of North America: <https://www.butterfliesandmoths.org>

Butterflies of America: <https://butterfliesofamerica.com>

eButterfly: <https://www.e-butterfly.org>

iNaturalist: <https://www.inaturalist.org>

NatureServe Explorer:

https://explorer.natureserve.org/Taxon/ELEMENT_GLOBAL.2.112629/Poanes_massasoit_chermocki

Nebraska Lepidoptera: <https://nebraskalepidoptera.com/massasoit2/>

The Lepidopterists' Society Season Summary:

<https://scan-bugs.org/portal/collections/individual/index.php?occid=44461465&clid=0>
